

IQTISODIYOT va TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

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XORIJIY TAJRIBA**

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KIRISH SO‘ZI

HURMATLI ANJUMAN ISHTIROKCHILARI, MEHMONLAR, HAMKASBLAR, AZIZ TALABALAR!

Sizlarni Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot instituti tomonidan tashkil etilayotgan mazkur Respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumanida qutlashdan mamnunmiz.

Qadrli anjuman ishtirokchilari, bugun biz mamlakatimizda biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash va iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish masalalari bo‘yicha amalga oshirilayotgan ishlar, mavjud muammolar va ularni bartaraf etish yo‘llari, hamda bu yo‘nalishdagi xorijiy tajribalarni muhokama qilish uchun to‘plandik.

Habaringiz bor, Prezidentimiz tomonidan 2024-yilni O‘zbekistonda “Yoshlar va biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash yili”, deb e‘lon qilinganida, inson qadrini ulug‘lash va aholimiz manfaatlarini ta‘minlash uchun kuchli iqtisodiyot barpo etish asosiy vazifalarimizdan biri ekanligi ta‘kidlangan edi.

Shunga ko‘ra, joriy yilda iqtisodiyotimizga xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishga, tadbirkorlik va xususiy mulk uchun keng imkoniyatlar yaratishga, ilm-fan, innovatsiya, IT kabi sohalarni, “yashil” va raqamli texnologiyalarni rivojlantirishga alohida e‘tibor qaratilmoqda.

Chunki, barqaror va kuchli iqtisodiyot nafaqat iqtisodiyot subyektlari uchun, balki jamiyatimizning kelajagi va farovonligi uchun ham juda katta ahamiyatga ega.

Hozirgi kunda, bizning jamiyatimiz - raqamli transformatsiya davriga qadam qo‘ydi. Raqamlashtirish jarayoni - biznes jarayonlaridan tortib, davlat xizmatlariga qadar ko‘plab sohalarni qamrab olmoqda.

Albatta bunday o‘zgarishlar, texnologik taraqqiyotga hamohang ravishda, qo‘shimcha imkoniyatlarni ochishga va rivojlanishning yangi strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishga keng imkoniyatlar yaratmoqda.

Lekin shu bilan bir qatorda, iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish va bunday sharoitda biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida, o‘ziga xos muammolar va turli savollar ham yuzaga kelmoqda.

Bunday masalalarni o‘rganib, uning yechimlarini topish uchun Toshkent menejment va iqtisodiyot institutining professor-o‘qituvchilari tomonidan ham turli ilmiy tadqiqotlarni olib borish yo‘lga qo‘yilgan. Ularning tadqiqotlari natijalaridan - o‘quv jarayonlarida, ta‘lim sifatini oshirish maqsadlarida, keng foydalaniladi.

Bu o‘z navbatida, institutda menejment, iqtisodiyot va axborot texnologiyalari sohasida tayyorlanadigan malakali mutaxassislarining nafaqat nazariy bilimlarini, balki amaliy ko‘nikmalarini ham oshirishga hizmat qiladi.

Bundan tashqari, institutda innovatsion dasturlar va loyihalar orqali talabalarni yangi texnologiyalar bilan tanishtirish, ularda raqamli iqtisodiyot va global biznes muhitida raqobatbardosh bo‘lish uchun zarur bo‘lgan ko‘nikmalarni shakllantirishga yordam beradi.

Bugungi anjumanda, biz raqamlashtirish va biznesni rivojlantirish jarayonlarida uchraydigan muammolarni chuqur o‘rganishni va ilmiy asoslangan yechimlarni izlashni o‘z oldimizga maqsad qilib qo‘yganmiz.

Shu bilan birga, asosiy anjuman va sho‘ba yig‘ilishlarida mazkur masalalar bo‘yicha xorijiy tajribalarni ham tahlil qilish orqali, biz qanday yechimlar topishimiz mumkinligini muhokama qilamiz.

Bugun sizlarning e‘tiboringizga taqdim etiladigan taqdimotlar va fikrlar - bizni zamonaviy iqtisodiyotning yangi talablariga mos keladigan biznes modellarni yaratishga ilhomlantiradi.

Maqsadimiz – bu kabi ilmiy-amaliy uchrashuvlar orqali ilm ahlini va biznes vakillarini bir joyda jamlab, biznesni qo‘llab-quvvatlash mexanizmlarini hamda iqtisodiyotni raqamlashtirish jarayonlarini yanada takomillashtirish bo‘yicha asoslangan takliflar va amaliy tavsiyalarni ishlab chiqishga imkoniyatlar yaratishdan iboratdir.

Biz bu jarayonda, o‘z tajribamizni almashish va birgalikda muammolarni hal qilish uchun yangi g‘oyalarni kashf etishni maqsad qilamiz.

Umid qilamanki, anjumanimiz samarali va foydali bo‘ladi.

Har biringizning ishtirokingiz va hissangiz bu jarayonda juda muhim.

Keling, birgalikda yangiliklarga ochiq bo‘lib, innovatsion yechimlarni izlaylik!

Bugungi anjuman ishiga va unda ishtirok etayotgan barcha ishtirokchilarning ilmiy-ijodiy faoliyatlariga ulkan muvaffaqiyatlar tilaymiz!

**Axmedov Xojiakbarxon Dilshatovich,
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3-SHO'BA. **MOLIYA VA SOLIQ SOHASIDAGI MUAMMOLAR,** **YECHIMLAR VA XORIJIY TAJRIBALAR**

ARE THE CURRENT RESEARCHED EARLY WARNING INDICATORS SIGNIFICANT IN IDENTIFYING BANKING CRISES?

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Abstract: This paper continues the discussion set forth in the paper "Initial research: Are the current researched early warning indicators significant in identifying banking crises?" by Berdiyrov (2024) with expanding on the paper: 'Early Warning Indicators of Banking Crises: Expanding the Family' by Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018). Using a pooled logistic model with large a data set from 1980 to 2019 containing multiple countries and crises and estimating the optimal thresholds for each indicator to produce accurate true signals of banking crises. I establish that the current EWIs, mainly the credit-to-GDP gap, are still highly significant and reliable indicators of banking crises, producing highly significant informative signals according to the AUROCs and signal-to-noise ratios. In addition, the additional indicators introduced in this paper are found to also be effective statistically significant indicators of vulnerabilities within the banking industry. For example, the loans-to-deposit has high AUCs across all time horizons and the highest signal-to-noise ratios amongst all the indicators.

Key words: Early Warning Indicators (EWIs), Banking Crises, pooled logistic model, AUROCs.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada Berdiyrovning (2024) "Dastlabki tadqiqotlar: HOZIRGI TADQIQOTLAR BANK KRIZLARINI ANIQLASH UCHUN ERTA OGOHLANTIRISH KO'RSATMALARI MUHIMMI?" maqolasida bayon etilgan muhokamani Aldasoro, Borio va Drehmann (2018) ning "Bank inqirozining erta ogohlantirish ko'rsatkichlari: kengaytirilgan muhokama" maqolasidagi fikrlar bilan davom ettiriladi. Ushbu maqola 1980 yildan 2019 yilgacha bir nechta mamlakatlar va ushbu mamlakatlardagi bank inqirozlarini o'z ichiga olgan katta ma'lumotlar to'plami bilan birlashtirilgan logistika modelidan foydalanadi va bank inqirozlarining aniq haqiqiy signallarini olish uchun har bir ko'rsatkich uchun optimal chegaralarni baholaydi. Ushbu maqolada EOKlar, asosan, kreditning YaIMga nisbati bank inqirozlarining juda muhim va ishonchli ko'rsatkichlaridan biri deb hisoblagan holda, AUROC va signal-to-noise nisbatlariga ko'ra juda muhim informatsion signallarni ishlab chiqarayotgani ko'rsatilgan. Bundan tashqari, ushbu maqolada keltirilgan qo'shimcha ko'rsatkichlar ham bank sohasidagi zaifliklarning statistik jihatdan muhim ko'rsatkichlar ekanligi aniqlandi. Misol uchun, kreditlarning depozitlarga nisbati barcha vaqt oralig'ida yuqori AUC va barcha ko'rsatkichlarning eng yuqori signal-shovqin nisbatlariga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: erta ogohlantirish ko'rsatkichlari (EOK), bank inqirozlari, qo'shma logistika modeli, AUROC.

Аннотация: В этой статье продолжается обсуждение, изложенное в статье «Начальное исследование: Являются ли текущие исследуемые индикаторы раннего предупреждения значимыми для выявления банковских кризисов?» Бердиев (2024) с расширением статьи: «Индикаторы раннего предупреждения банковских кризисов: расширение семьи» Альдасоро, Борьо и Дрехманна (2018). Использование объединенной логистической модели с большим набором данных с 1980 по 2019 год, содержащим несколько стран и кризисов, и оценка оптимальных пороговых значений для каждого индикатора для получения точных истинных сигналов банковских кризисов. Я считаю, что текущие ИПП, в основном разрыв между кредитом и ВВП, по-прежнему являются весьма значимыми и надежными индикаторами банковских кризисов, производя весьма значимые информативные сигналы в соответствии с AUROC и отношениями сигнал/шум. Кроме того, дополнительные индикаторы, представленные в этой статье, также оказались эффективными статистически значимыми индикаторами уязвимостей в банковской отрасли. Например, кредиты к депозитам имеют высокие AUC на всех временных горизонтах и самые высокие коэффициенты сигнал/шум среди всех индикаторов.

Ключевые слова: индикаторы раннего предупреждения (ИПП), банковские кризисы, объединенная логистическая модель, AUROC.

INTRODUCTION

I will follow upon on the argument proposed by Berdiyrov (2024) and in this paper, I will focus on the early warning indicators of a banking crisis, assessing the significance of the already well-established indicators. I will use secondary data and expand upon a base paper that tests the statistical significance and reliability of leading indicators that signal upcoming banking crises years prior. In the past severe banking crises have not been avoided and they cause decremental harm to the whole economy. In addition, in the modern century, banking regulations are continuously changing, and banks are now more vulnerable to international markets; so, my aim is to assess if the leading indicators of a banking crisis are still valuable and if not, do they need to be updated to the new regulations and operations of the whole banking systems.

The core objective of this paper is to evaluate the significance of the leading indicators of a banking crisis using a base paper. Using statistical tests like the receiver operating characteristic curve method to fully map type I and type II errors of each indicator. And the AUC to estimate the signalling quality of a binary signal. However, I will only be assessing a small sample of indicators (9 indicators) and data from a limited number of countries. In reality, there are lots of indicators policymakers use to assess the probability of potential banking crises, volatility in the domestic currency or supervision/regulations of banking operations, which may limit the generalisability of the findings from this paper.

The structure of the paper is split into 4 parts. Part 1 is the literature review, focusing on reviewing past research on the leading indicators of a banking crisis and the criticism of the past research, any suggested advancement in the research or models that should be included when evaluating the significance of important indicators of a banking crisis. Part 2 focuses on the methodology section of the paper, outlining the procedure of data collection and how I am conducting the analyse of the testing the significance of the indicators using ROC and the AUC. Part 3 highlights the findings of the methodology section, evaluating the results of the ROC curves and the signal-to-noise ratios for each indicator and explaining in detail according to the results why these indicators are significant in signalling a banking crisis. And finally, Part 4 concludes the paper and finalises what the findings from this paper means for the significance of leading indicators of a banking crisis and highlighting specific indicators that should be used by policymakers to predict future banking crises.

LITERATURE REVIEW

In this paper, I will be taking an existing model from the research paper “Early warning indicators of banking crises: expanding the family” by Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018), and re-estimating it with additional variables. In this paper, the authors use the signal extraction and multivariate probit panel regression models to statistically investigate the performance of change in the credit to GDP ratio as a useful indicator of a systematic banking crisis. The findings reveal that the advancement of the financialisation of economies leads to the supply of excess credit that generates conditions that increase the likelihood of systematic banking crises, even with persistently low and stable inflation.

The superiority of this paper is that before Drehmann et al conduct the statistical analysis of the usefulness of early warning indicators such the credit-to-GDP gap or household debt service ratio (DSR), the researchers assess the EWI performance of both household and international debt and map the statistical analysis into current conditions taking into account aggregate indicators, to provide a highly critical evaluation of debt categories as early warning indicators for systematic banking crises. However, there is a gap in the data sample for this study, only 27 out of 42 jurisdictions often only starting from the mid-1990s have data for household DSR so the statistical results for household DSR may show a different insignificant long-run trend around the crises in the chosen time horizon compared to the other indicators in this study. Also, this paper only evaluates household and cross-border credit variables as potential leading indicators of a banking crisis, despite the fact that fellow highly recognised researchers have statistically proven that macroeconomic-financial variables are also credible indicators of banking crises. Therefore, this paper does not provide a well-rounded argument on leading EWIs of banking crises. Concluding, that you can still “expand the family” on the subject of early warning indicators of banking crises.

The credit-to-GDP gap is highly regarded as an important early warning indicator for banking crises. There have been lots of papers that have researched the development of credit-to-GDP gap as a reliable and significant indicator of a banking crisis. One paper written by Drehmann (2013) used a large sample of 39 emerging market and advanced economies starting from 1970 that captures 33 crises and concluded that the credit-to-GDP gap is a valuable early warning indicator for systematic banking crises as they easily identify vulnerabilities in the environment or help policymakers in the implementation of monetary and fiscal policies when dealing with countercyclical capital buffers. The article also established that by considering all the sources of credit in both public and private sectors rather than just considering bank credit, the accuracy

of systemic banking crises significantly increases. Another paper by Vidal-Abarca and Ruiz (2015) used a lot more statistical methods than most of the papers based on the early warning indicators of banking crises. The authors of this paper estimated the accuracy and reliability of credit as an effective signal of banking crises using a large sample size containing 83 developed and emerging economies and lots of statistical methods. They used a Bayesian Model Average technique through a multivariate framework and AUROC and noise to signal ratios through a univariate regression model, for both in-sample and out-of-sample forecasting methods. All the methods statistically found that the credit-to-GDP gap outperforms all the other credit indicators in the model. So, it is very important to include credit-to-GDP gap as a variable in the quantitative analysis in this paper when evaluating the significance of the current early warning indicators.

The debt service ratio (DSR) is also established in past papers to be a valid EWI of a banking crisis. Defined as the proportion of interest payments and loan repayments to income, so it captures the liquidity constraint of individual households or the whole economy. Drehmann and Juselius (2014) quantitatively analysed data from 26 countries from 1980 to 2012 and found that the DSR produces strong signals two years before a banking crisis, especially in the last four quarters where the DSR is a near perfect indicator, the AUCs are between 0.94 to 1.00. The DSR is established to be a highly significant indicator in the short run. This is also confirmed by another paper written by Drehmann and Juselius in 2012, the DSR has a stable signalling performance during a 5-year time horizon with high AUROCs (around 0.9) in the short-run and lower AUCs as the forecasted horizon increases. However, Drehmann and Juselius (2012) fail to distinguish between total and household DSR and to investigate if specific types of DSR perform better as indicators. As outlined by Drehmann et al (2018) in the base paper, that evaluated total and household DSR as indicators of banking crises and concluded that household DSR produces more true positive signals in the short period compared to total DSR that has a higher rate of accurate true positives in the long run.

There have been numerous papers discussing the importance of the loans-to-deposit ratio, property prices, real growth of GDP, inflation rate in checking the likelihood of financial crisis.

Even though, papers have carried out extensive research on the early warning indicators of banking crises and highlighted highly significant early warning indicators of banking crises, they have not been successful implemented by policymakers to help avoid severe banking crises such the Great Financial Crisis 2007-2009 which was a result of the collapse of the American and British banking system and recently the failure of big US banks in early 2023. Prior to the crisis, the Federal Reserve began to increase interests to contract the economy, causing bond prices to decline, which decreased the market value of bank capital reserves, causing some banks to incur unrealised losses to main liquidity. Silicon Valley Bank was forced to sell its bonds for financial stability, triggering panic by bank depositors and creditors leading to a banking crisis in the US; (Admati, et al., 2023). A surge in inflation and rapidly rising interest rates are demonstrated to be significant early warning indicators of a banking crisis but they weren't detected by policy makers and the crisis was not averted. This could be because papers on the EWIs of a banking crisis have only highlighted the leading indicators of banking crisis and have not discussed how the government or the central bank can implement policies to use the indicators to signal the possibility of a crisis within the banking industry and combat crises years prior to the crisis. And the logit/probit model used extensively by most studies still suffer from methodological issues, the definition of financial crisis as a dummy variable leads to a weak assumption when constructing the model and the single-step estimation leads to biased results when estimating EWIs of banking crises. So, research that incorporates more statistical methods should be considered when assessing the significance of EWIs of banking crises.

For example, a paper written by Bryde-Erichsen (2016) analysed the noise-to-signal ratio as a tool by policymakers for evaluation of indicators. The noise-to-signal ratio was discovered to be a useless tool for indicator evaluation. When assessing the appropriate noise-to-signal ratio, optimal thresholds should be implemented by policymakers as they are very important to increasing the accuracy of the signals and reducing the number of false signals of banking crises. With a low threshold value for the indicator, it will issue more false signals and with a higher threshold the probability of not signalling an upcoming crisis will increase. So, the noise-to-signal ratio or signal-to-noise ratio approach is a valid statistical method to use to assess the significance of leading indicators of a banking crisis.

Past papers have statistically analysed data from the time horizon of past banking crises to estimate and assess the statistical significance of early warning indicators of banking crises. Hardy and Pazarbasioglu (1999) used a sample that covered 38 countries which suffered a total of 43 financial cycles of banking system crises. And when researching the significance of total credit as early warning indicator for systematic banking crises, Drehmann (2013) used 33 crises from 1970 in their data sample. Every banking crisis is different and is a result of different financial indicators, the banking crisis from 2007 was a result of mismanagement of funds by banking authorities and the Spanish banking crisis starting in 2008 was due to macro-financial imbalances such as excessive credit growth or excessive risk-taking in the financial industry. So, it is unreliable to estimate EWIs from studies on past banking crises to predict future crises and apply them to all types of banking crises.

And a main reason why past research on significant early earning indicators of banking crises has not been successfully used to completely avoid future banking crises, just helped to deflate the severe consequences of bank failure in economies. So, it is important to clarify what type of financial crises are in the data sets when using them to evaluate the accuracy of EWI signals for specific financial crises such as banking crises.

METHODOLOGY

In this paper, I will follow the research methodology recommendations proposed by Berdiyurov (2024). I will be using a pooled logistic regression model to illustrate the accuracy of the five chosen indicators of a banking crises as outlined above and in the literature review. The benefits of using a pooled logistic regression are that multiple indicators can be easily observed quarterly over multiple years and we can clearly identify risk factors associated between the early warning indicators and banking crises. To test the significance of the chosen early warning indicator whilst estimating the results, I will use the p-value with a significance level of 5% generated from the logit regression for each indicator's database. If the p-value is less than the significance level of 5% then the indicator is statistically significant and produces credible signals of banking crises.

To assess the performance of EWIs in this paper, I will use a statistical software (R studio) to map type I and type II errors for the statistical tests of each indicator. This full mapping is referred to as the receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curve, which measures the proportion of actual positives that are correctly identified by early warning indicators such as household credit-to-GDP gap and the property price gap. The area under the curve (AUC) is estimated to measure the signalling quality of a binary (yes/no) signal. In this paper, the AUC ranges between 0 and 1 using an optimal threshold to assess the accuracy of the individual indicators when predicting a banking crisis. An uninformative indicator has an AUC of 0.5, whilst a perfect indicator has an AUC of 1.0. An informative and statistically significant indicator ranges from 0.5 to 1.0.

However, even if an indicator has a significant AUC, correct signalling of any upcoming banking crisis relies on policymakers implementing optimal thresholds for each indicator. The policymakers must choose an optimal threshold that minimises the noise-to-signal ratio (ratio of false alarms to correctly predicted events) or else the indicators will be unable to detect vulnerabilities within the domestic banking system three years prior to a crisis. So, in this paper, I will build upon Drehmann et al (2018) paper with additional indicators and estimate AUCs of the individual indicators, with the consideration of optimal thresholds.

Results and Discussions

For an early warning indicator to be a highly significant and reliable indicator of upcoming banking crises according to Drehmann and Juselius (2014) it must fulfil three main criteria of effective indicators in the context of macroprudential policymaking. Firstly, it must provide signals early for policy measures to take effect. Secondly, it must not be unstable between signalling a crisis and being "off" so has a probability of correctly identifying trends. And finally, it must be easy to interpretate by policy makers. The credit-to-GDP gap fulfils all these criteria, as shown in Figure 1. It provided a signal to policymakers about an upcoming banking crisis about 2-3 years prior to crisis, when it increased above the optimal threshold of 9.0 and it remained stable above the threshold until two years after the crisis in 2010.

FIGURE 1¹: Credit-to-GDP gap relative to the critical threshold:

1 Figure 1 shows the evolution of the average credit-to-GDP gap since 1980. The first red vertical line highlights the three years before the banking crisis in 2007 the period policymakers would like to see a signal based on the assumed three-year prediction horizon. The second red line shows the end of the post-crisis in 2010. Drehmann et al (2018) outline that the optimal threshold for the Credit-to-GDP gap is 9 (dashed blue line) on Figure 1. In the pre-crisis period, the gap exceeded 9, so the prediction rate is 100% (Data: [BIS Statistics](#)).

FIGURE 2²: ROC curve for the average credit-to-GDP gap:

When excluding the credit-to-GDP variable from the rest of the indicators in the data sample, the ROC curve has an accuracy rating for correct signals of 0.9375 and has an exceedingly high rate of true positives and a really low rate of false positives, as shown by Figure 2. The area under the curve (AUC) is 0.9667, which is close to 1, highlighting that the credit-to-GDP gap is an effective and combined measure of sensitivity and specificity.

These results are also statistically significant and reliable results as the logistic regression model used to estimate these results has a p-value below the 5% significance (p-value: 0.035).

Assessing the optimal thresholds

When assessing the performance of EWIs, it is vital to first consider the optimal thresholds for the noise-to-signal tests of each indicator. The base paper outlines that the optimal threshold for the credit-to-GDP gap indicator is 9. The authors outline that if the threshold is lowered from 9 to 4, the number of false alarms increases. This is proven by Figure 3, the ROC curve shows a higher rate of false positive alarms compared to true positives, the curve is also closer to the 45° line. And the accuracy rate for the ROC curve falls to 0.8021 and the AUC is now 0.6213. Providing less informative signals to policymakers on upcoming crises.

Figure 3: Credit-to-GDP gap ROC curve with threshold of 4:

Predictive power of single EWIs using the AUC

To evaluate the performance of individual indicators without the influence of external factors, I will use

² Figure 2 shows the ROC curve of the Average Credit-to-GDP gap for all the countries in the sample along with a 45° line.

the pooled logistic model for each indicator to estimate the AUCs in correspondence to the optimal thresholds which are based on specific policymakers' preferences.

Table 1 outlines the descriptive statistics and statistical coefficients for the data sample of each indicator. Total DSR has the lowest standard deviation figure of 2.9, representing that the values in the data sample across 17 variables are close the mean. Whilst the data sample for the inflation rate has the highest standard deviation (21.1), indicating that the values are spread out over a wider range and are further away from the mean, so extreme values of rates of inflation occur more frequently.

Table 1³: Descriptive Statistics & Statistical Coefficients

INDICATORS	Statistics				Coefficients			
	No of obs	No of variables	Mean	Std.Var	Estimate	Std.Error	Z-value	Pr(> z)
Credit-to-GDP Gap	160	25	1.3029	7.4297	0.5891	0.1200	4.908	0.000838
Total DSR	160	17	85.249	15.567	0.11784	0.02318	5.084	0.000374
Property Price Gap	84	19	70.860	2.8733	0.10950	0.08557	1.280	0.000201
Loans/Deposit Gap	80	12	124.82	9.6823	0.4372	0.1224	3.571	0.000356
Inflation Rate	160	23	75.706	21.081	0.05526	0.01673	3.303	0.000957

All the indicators have p-values (Pr(>|z|)) less than the significance levels of 1% and 5%, indicating that the AUCs results in Table 2 for all the indicators are statistically significant and less influenced by methodological issues.

Table 2⁴: A Comparison of the Predictive Power of Individual EWIs using the AUC:

EARLY WARNING INDICATORS (EWIs)	Horizon (quarters)											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
Credit-to-GDP Gap	1.00	0.99	0.99	0.98	0.99	0.98	0.97	0.91	0.90	0.90	0.86	0.81
Total DSR	0.91	0.86	0.81	0.78	0.77	0.76	0.73	0.72	0.67	0.67	0.63	0.54
Property Price Gap	0.96	0.95	0.94	0.93	0.90	0.87	0.83	0.77	0.76	0.74	0.69	0.67
Loans-to-Deposit Gap	1.00	0.98	0.99	0.99	0.96	0.98	0.99	0.94	0.95	0.97	0.92	0.92
Inflation Rate	0.90	0.95	0.86	0.85	0.84	0.83	0.75	0.74	0.72	0.69	0.64	0.61

The credit-to-GDP gap and the loans-to-deposit gap have the highest AUCs across all the forecast horizons, with an AUC of 1.0 in the first horizon and lowest AUCs of 0.81 and 0.92, which are representatives of a fully informative signal, with a true positive rate of 100%. Further emphasising the point that that credit-to-GDP gap is informative signal of upcoming financial vulnerabilities around three years before the banking crises. Alongside, the theory that the loan-to-deposit is an important additional indicator that should be considered by policymakers when implementing models to accurately forecast potential banking crises.

The total debt service ratio (DSR) defined as the ratio of interest payments plus amortisations to income, performs particularly well two years before crises, but then one year before crises, the indicator becomes less

³ All the information on the sample sets for each indicator for findings on the predictive power of single EWIs using the AUC is in the Appendix Table A1.

⁴ Use a 12-quarter forecast horizon as we can only use indicators to assess the build-up of vulnerabilities within a multi-year horizon and not exactly identify the precise time and date of a banking crisis. Some of the optimal thresholds used when estimating the AUC are 80% for the loan-to-deposit ratio and 2% for the target inflation rate.

accurate with AUCs around 0.6 to 0.5, signalling a higher rate of false positive rates compared to the rates of true positive in the longer horizon.

The property price gap performs better as an EWI for banking crises than the total DSR, as shown in Table 2, the AUCs for the property prices are all higher than the AUCs for total DSRs across all time horizons and are close to a perfect signal with figures 0.96 to 0.90 for the first 5 quarters prior to a banking crisis. They only fall to 0.69 and 0.67 in the last two quarters prior to the crisis, providing policymakers with informative signals and sufficient time to implement policies in the economy to reduce the impact of a crisis on domestic banks.

The other additional indicator, the inflation rate measured the CPI performs similar to the property price gap indicator, it has high AUCs for all the horizons, especially in the first quarter horizons. The ROC curves for the inflation rate have high rates of true positives for the first quarters but then the rate of accuracy and the number of true positives falls sooner and faster than the property price gap in the last six quarters prior to crises, with AUCs of 0.75 to 0.61. Communicating less informative and unstable signals to policymakers in the long term compared to the other indicators.

In summary, according to the AUCs in Table 2 all the individual early warning indicators in this paper provide highly accurate informative signals (AUCs more than 0.5) to policymakers on the build-up of vulnerabilities within the banking industry; providing them with effective resources and sufficient time to reduce the severity of any upcoming banking crises.

Predictive power of EWIs using the signal-to-noise ratio

Another method to assess the forecasting power of indicators is by comparing the signalling performance of the individual indicators at the optimal thresholds as chosen by a particular loss function. A threshold is selected to minimise the loss function, defined as the percentage of true crises mis-signalled (Type I) and the percentage of falsely flagged crises (Type II), of indicators when signalling a banking crisis. The signal-to-noise ratio is the relationship between the share of accurately identified crises and non-crises (signals), and the share of missed identified crises and false alarms (noise).

$$\text{Signal-to-Noise Ratio}^5 (\text{SNR}) = \frac{\text{Number of correctly identified crises}}{\text{Number of missed identified crises} + \text{Number of false alarms}}$$

Table 3: Individual EWIs using the Signal-to-Noise Ratio and the Optimal Threshold

EARLY WARNING INDICATORS (EWIs)	Threshold (1)	Predicted (2)	SNR (3)	No of crises (4)
Credit-to-GDP gap	9.0	85.0	1.07	30
Total DSR	1.8	68.0	0.98	28
Property Price Gap	11.0	66.0	0.99	23
Loans-to-Deposit Gap	0.8	79.5	1.29	13
Inflation Rate	0.02	67.9	0.88	26

Results were obtained using a pooled logistic model for each indicator to estimate the signal-to-noise ratios using optimal thresholds. The no of observations and variables for all the five indicators are the same as the sample sizes used when estimating the AUCs in Table 1. All the variables/indicators are independent from each other to avoid autocorrelation and prevent external factors from influencing the results. An in-depth explanation of the main characteristics for each estimate in the sample used to calculate the findings in Table 3 is in the Appendix Table A1.

Table 3 shows the predictive power of the indicators based on the chosen thresholds criteria by Drehmann et al (2018). It shows the values of the noise-to-signal for the different individual indicators subject to the correct predictability of crises. The better early warning indicator will tend to have the higher signal-to-noise ratio, which in this case is the loans-to-deposit gap. The indicator captures around 80% of crises with a signal to noise ratio of roughly 1.27 across the sample. According to the quarterly data from 2000 with 13 crises, the signal-to-noise ratio of the loans-to-deposit gap with a threshold of 80% signalled the GFC three years prior to the crisis. Confirming the point that loans-to-deposit gap is an important additional EWI that should be taken into account by policymakers to forecast upcoming banking crises.

The signal-to-noise ratio also confirms the results from Table 2, the credit-to-GDP gap, which has the highest number of banking crises (33) in their data sample compared to other indicators, not only has a high

5 Results are based on the largest data sample for each indicator. (1) The optimal threshold that minimised the signal-to-noise ratio while capturing at least 66% of the crises. (2) Percentage of correctly predicted crises. A crisis is correctly identified if the indicator breaches the threshold anytime within a three-year horizon before the crisis. (3) Signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio. (4) Number of crises included in this sample.

AUC across all the time horizons, the indicator also has a high SNR and accurately captures around 85% of banking crises in the data sample in respective of the optimal threshold of 9.0. The credit-to-GDP gap has a higher share of accurately identified crises and non-crises than the share of missed identified crises and false alarms.

According to the signal-to-noise ratio, the performance of total DSR and property prices as early warning indicators of banking crises are closely equivalent, they have similar SNRs and predict 68% and 66% of banking crises. However, the sample for property prices includes a lower occurrence of financial crises. The other additional indicator included in this paper, the rate of inflation has the lowest SNR with a ratio of 0.88 and predicts the lowest percentage of correctly predicted crises at 67.9%, even though the optimal threshold of 2% is established to be the optimal rate in most advanced economies and is regularly used by monetary authorities to control economic conditions.

The indicators in Table 2, all have signal-to-noise ratios above 0.80 and capture at least 66% of crisis for the chosen time horizons of each indicator. A SNR greater than or close to 1.0 imply that the signal is stronger than the noise. Supporting the claim that these indicators are trustworthy leading EWIs of banking crises.

The results from Table 2, also highlight the robustness of the EWIs. Despite different time horizons for all the indicators, i.e., the sample size for the credit-to-GDP and other indicators starts from 1980 and the sample for the loans-to-deposit gap starts from 2000, the thresholds for each indicator are the same. This shows that these results are not solely due to unexpected severe crises related to the GFC in 2008. And are robust to performing bivariate comparisons for each pair of indicators.

Combined indicators

Past papers have shown that combining information from credit and asset markets into composite indicators can improve the performance of indicators as reliable signals of a banking crisis. It has been proven in the past that extreme movements in credit growth (e.g., lending boom) and in asset prices (e.g., housing bubble) are both main causes of banking crises. So, we should assess the performance of combined indicators as leading indicators of banking crises, using optimal thresholds for combinations of debt variable and property prices.

For a warning signal to be issued we require the indicator for debt to be breach the threshold and the property price gap indicator to be above 11 within three years prior to the breach of the threshold. The gap of 11 is chosen because Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018) outline that 11 is the critical threshold obtained for this variable based on predicting at least 66% of the crises.

Table 4⁶: The predictive power of combined EWIs using the Signal-to-Noise Ratio and the Optimal signalling thresholds: Credit and Property prices.

EARLY WARNING INDICATORS (EWIs)	Threshold (1)	Predicted (with property price gap at 11) (2)	SNR (3)	% change in SNR (4)
Credit-to-GDP Gap	4.0	80	1.40	30.8
Total DSR	0.4	70	1.16	18.4
Loans-to-Deposit Gap	0.8	81	1.60	24.0

As shown in Table 4, combining information from credit and property price gaps improves the accuracy of EWIs for banking crises. The signal-to-noise ratios for the credit variables with an optimal threshold based on a property price gap of 11, increases by a min of 18% and by a max of 31%. For the combined early warning indicators of banking crises, there is a higher probability of signalling accurate crises than the loss functions and number of false positives. For some indicators, the combined indicators also predict a higher percentage of correctly predicted crises and less false alarms. For example, the percentage of correctly predicted signals of the loans-to-deposit gap as EWI of banking crises is now 81%, an increase of 1.5%.

Potential correlation between indicators

To expand even further on the Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018) and to further assess the significance of the current leading EWIs of banking crises it is beneficial to consider the correlation between the early warning indicators in this paper. An early warning indicator may cause other indicators to move above the optimal threshold and generate further signals to policymakers on upcoming banking crises. The correlation

6 (1) The optimal threshold that minimises the signal-to-noise ratio while capturing at least 66% of the crises. (2) Percentage of correctly predicted crises. (3) Signal-to-noise (SNR) ratio. (4) Percentage change in the signal-to-noise ratios from the individual (Table 2) to combined indicators.

between indicators may amplify the number of informative signals or may create more false alarms that lead to a mismanagement of tools by policymakers.

For example, the credit-to-GDP gap and the property price gap tend to influence each other. When there is a credit crunch in an economy during a recession, there is likely to be an after-shock on the housing market. As limited borrowing and spending in an economy limits the disposable income of individuals and banks in the domestic financial market, reducing the demand for real estate in the economy and therefore leading to a sharp fall in overall property prices. This has recently been proven in the past three years from 2020 to 2023 in the UK, when the actual credit-to-GDP gap started to decrease from a peak of 175.5 in the first quarter of 2021 to 151.4 in the last quarter of 2023 and real property prices started to decrease later in the third quarter of 2021 by 2.5%; (*Data gathered from the BIS online database*).

The correlation between the credit-to-GDP gap and the property price gap also helps policymakers to determine the structure of the build-up of vulnerabilities within the banking system before the crisis. So, they can easily identify any weaknesses in the domestic banking and prevent any upcoming banking crises.

The inflation rate also tends to influence property prices. In the short-run, when the inflation rate increases due to excess spending in the economy, it can cause a limited supply of properties available in the market that leads to excessive demand, which eventually results in a rise in prices of property above the rate of inflation, (Hodgkinson, 2023). The relationship between these two indicators is also indicated in a study by Ahearne et al (2005) when they analysed cross-country economic data from the 20th century. They outlined that in both the pre-1985 and post-1985 samples, the downturn in property prices was closely associated with declines in the rate of inflation that began one or two years after the peak in property prices.

So, it is important to policymakers that when they implement effective EWIs into their agendas, they should firstly evaluate and identify any correlations between the individual indicators, so there are no false alarms and clear correct signals of forthcoming banking crises. Identifying whether there is a correlation between indicators may also point out any new indicators that policymakers have failed to address as significant early warning indicators of banking crises. Improving their ability to successfully implement policies to manage any weakness in the domestic banking market and avoid any severe crises.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In conclusion, by expanding on the paper by Aldasoro, Borio and Drehmann (2018), the current researched leading early warning indicators including the additional indicators are still highly significant and reliable indicators of banking crises. The statistical analysis conducted in the paper proved that all the five indicators, the credit-to-GDP gap, property price gap, loans-to-deposit gap, inflation rate and total DSR generated informative signals of banking crises. They all had high signal-to-noise ratios and correctly predicted a high percentage (at least 66%) of banking crises.

The credit-to-GDP gap indicator was once again proven to be an important EWI of banking crises. The findings in Table 3 and 4 reflect the analysis from past papers analysed in the literature review. The credit-to-GDP gap was found to have highly informative signals with near perfect AUCs, generating highly accurate signals of banking crises with a low rate of false alarms. The indicator also had the second highest signal-to-noise ratios and predicted the highest percentage of correctly identified crises for both the individual and combined indicators analysis. Thus, a sharp increase in any accumulated debt or an unexpected decrease in the overall GDP level represent severe vulnerabilities within the domestic banking system that may result in a harsh banking crisis. So, the credit-to-GDP is still a significant leading EWI of banking crises that policymakers should monitor in the short and long-run.

The findings in this paper also emphasize my claim beforehand that the base paper used in this paper is not fully representative of leading indicators of banking crises and should be further expanded upon. The loans-to-deposit gap of national banks and the inflation rate are proven in this paper to be statistically significant unsupervised indicators that should be explored by policymakers when implementing effective EWIs to signal upcoming banking crises in most countries. Along with credit-to-GDP gap, the loans-to-deposit gap had the highest rates for the Area Under the Receiver Operating Characteristics curves (AUROCs) and the signal-to-noise ratios (SNR), in respect to the optimal thresholds, for both the individual and combined indicators; indicating that it is the most significant indicators. The loans-to-deposit gap also predicted the highest percentage of correctly predicted crises. In summary, low reserve accounts and excessing borrowing within the domestic banking sector may represent any unrealised weaknesses that if not managed may materialise into banking crises. So, it is vital that policymakers monitor the loans-to-deposit gaps of domestic banks to predict banking crises years before.

The inflation rate is also shown to be a significant indicator of a banking crisis. With one of the biggest datasets containing 26 banking crises amongst all the indicators, the inflation rate correctly predicted around

68% of banking crises within the sample and had high AUCs in the short run. But the inflation rate had the lowest figures in all the statistical models in this paper. This could be because the rate of inflation tends to be extremely high three years before the crisis when there is excessive spending in the economy but then just one year prior to the crisis it tends to be lower, so it is not normally a stable indicator. The inflation rate is also time consuming to control within the economy, the use of interest rates by the central bank to stabilise the inflation rate takes up to 18 months to come into effect. So even though in the long run it is an effective and significant indicator, in the short-term policymakers may find it difficult to monitor the inflation rate monthly and to effectively implement into the economy.

In closing, the current researched leading early warning indicators are confirmed to be statistically significant and highly accurate indicators of banking crises. But there is still further research that can be carried out by policymakers on additional indicators that may be important and more effective indicators. The inflation rate and loans-to-deposit gap are statistically proven in this paper to be additional significant early warning indicators of banking crises. But there are still other additional indicators that should be researched and assessed to be leading indicators of banking crises.

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